

Enhanced Parameter Observation of OR Gate Structured 8x8 Bit Array Implementation with Voltage Variation for High Speed Application

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Abstract - SRAM cells have been the leading technologies used to implement memory cells in computer systems, each one having its benefits and limitations. For power constrained designs low voltage SRAMs are critical issue. Presently, the choice of supply voltage in SRAMs is directed by bit cell readability, writability, data retention etc. However, the choice of supply voltage influences the reliability of SRAMs in the nanometer technology nodes as well. Two important reliability challenges for present and upcoming generation SRAMs are gate oxide degradation. We have examined the supply voltage variation on design parameters. We have fabricated OR gate structured 8x8 bit 7T SRAM Array using various access time and frequencies with different supply voltages in 45 nm CMOS process technology. We have estimated leakage current, leakage power, Dynamic current, Dynamic power and efficiency of OR gate structured 8x8 bit 7T SRAM Array. The goal of this paper is to reduce the power and increase the efficiency of the Static Random Access Memory array while maintaining the competitive performance.

Keywords – ARRAY; CMOS; Leakage Power; Leakage Current; Dynamic Current; Dynamic Power; SRAM.

1. Introduction

Expansions in CMOS technology have made it possible to design chips for high integration density, fast performance, and low power consumption. To achieve these objectives, the feature size of CMOS devices has been radically scaled to very small features and dimensions [1]. Leakage Power, Dynamic Power, Leakage Current and Dynamic Current are one of the most significant parameters in VLSI designs. In a CMOS digital circuit, power consumption is dominated by dynamic power, which is proportional to the square of the supply voltage. As a result variation in supply voltage is obviously an active technique in power reduction. Due to high density and Power consumption of SRAMs accounts for a important portion of the overall chip, low power operation is a feature that has become a requirement in today's microprocessors; hence, power consumption of SRAM modules must be reduced and has been under extensive exploration in the technical literature [2].

Device reduction and the quickly developing demand for mobile or power-aware systems have resulted in a crucial need to reduce power supply voltage (V_{dd}). However, with decreasing signal charge voltage reduction along with device scaling are associated. Moreover, increasing intra-die process parameter variations, predominantly random dopant threshold voltage variations can lead to large number of fails in particularly small channel are a memory designs. SRAM cells are adversely affected, due to their small size and large numbers on chip. This tendency is predictable to grow significantly as designs are scaled further with each technology generation [3]. Predominantly, it conflicts with the Need to preserve a high signal to noise ratio, or high noise Margins, in SRAM strand is one of the major impairments to creating a stable cell at low voltage. When combined with other effects such as narrow width effects, temperature, and process variations and parasitic transistor resistance, the scaling of SRAMs becomes progressively difficult due to reduced margins

[4]. A variation in Supply Voltage gives significant advantages in digital Circuits by virtue of the CV2DD active energy savings. Of Course, the ensuing reduction in the operating speed also means that a particular circuit block takes longer to complete a required operation. As a result, the leakage power, which comes about as a result of the idle subV_{th} currents, integrates over a longer time, and the leakage energy goes up. This opposing trend give rise to a minimum energy supply voltage, which, for most practical digital circuits, occurs below the threshold voltage of the devices [5]. Variation in supply voltage is virtually nullified. Higher fail Probabilities occur due to variation voltage , and low voltage Operation is becoming problematic as higher supply voltages Are required to conquer these process variations .To overcome These challenges ,recent industry trends have learned to wards exploring larger cells and more exotic SRAM circuit styles in Scaled technologies[6]. Examples are the use of write-assist design, read- modify- write, read-assist designs [7]. Many circuit-level techniques have been proposed to lower VDD MIN for on-chip caches based on conventional SRAM cells [8]. The popular supply-voltage reduction technique can reduce the leakage power. However, supply-voltage reduction increases the failure-rate of stored data. Stored SRAM-cell data faces the following failure mechanisms: (i) parametric failures like read-upset, access-time failure, etc. due to process-variations, (ii) supply noise induced failures, (iii) gate-leakage fluctuation due to trapped charge in gate oxide, and (iv) any permanent defects. With the exception of any permanent defects, other failure mechanisms increase with supply voltage reduction [9]. Thus, any variation in supply voltage based leakage power and dynamic power reduction is attained at the cost of lower data-reliability. Supply voltage has been scaled down in order to keep the power consumption under control. Hence, the transistor threshold voltage has to be commensurately scaled to preserve a high drive current and achieve performance enhancement .However, the threshold voltage scaling results in the considerable increase of the Subthreshold leakage current [10].These techniques either put on different supply voltages or use special supporting circuits for read and write operations to reduce the failure probability of SRAM cells [11]. These techniques reduced the failure chance by orders of greatness, but at the cost of added particular circuitry and additional design complexity. In a separate approach, micro- architecture techniques have been proposed to cope with the VDDMIN challenge [12]. .Among these, supply voltage down scaling offers the Highest effectiveness since the dynamic power is a quadratic function of voltage .Moreover, it also exponentially reduces The leakage current which directs the active current in the sub-100 nm CMOS processes. Supply voltage scaling has recently extended to sub threshold circuit operations to deeply reduce the total power consumption [13]. As a result, a Substantial amount of energy has been saved, at the cost of speed Performance .Several silicon results have been successfully measured at 0.3V or lower [14].However, it is uncertain to additional scale down the supply voltage that provides minimum energy consumption is characteristically observed in the sub threshold region since the speed is exponentially degraded and hence total energy per read/write is Increased [15].

In this paper we present the OR gate structured 8x8 7T SRAM cell Array using various access time 4ns and 8ns with frequencies 0.25GHZ and 0.125GHZ respectively with different supply voltages 0.3 v, 0.5v, 0.7v .Here, optimum voltage supply is 0.7v and nominal voltage supply is 0.3v.We study the various parameters like leakage current , leakage power, dynamic current , dynamic power , operating current, operating power and efficiency of the SRAM Array.

2. Memory Structure

The 8 X8 bit memory array using OR gate structure was designed and simulated .The memory structure is as shown in Figure.1. Each block of the array 7T SRAM cell, there are 8 rows and 8

columns arranged to form an 8x8 SRAM cell array. To address these rows of cells the decoder is used proceeding to the array arrangement. The AND gate and inverter based 3:8 CMOS decoder is used to generate the address lines. These address lines are the word line and bitline which are connected to each row and column of the 8x8 array. Outputs of every column in array are connected to the 8 input OR gate. The output of 8x8 bit cells are connected to the OR gate and the output of OR gate is final output of 8x8 bit SRAM Cell Array .With variation in supply voltage, different recognizing becomes more unreliable with leakage current and dynamic current from unaccessed cells causing variation on the reference bitline . The control signals wordlines and bitlines select are .7v .5v and .3v [16].

Figure 1. Schematic of OR gate structure 8x8 7T SRAM Array

A. 7T SRAM Cell

In 8x8 7T SRAM array we used 7T SRAM cell which provides high read stability. This section shows the high read stability 7T SRAM cell in which the read and write transistors are not mutually interact with each other, in this manner we can achieve high read stability. This SRAM topology is suitable for low voltage regime. NMOS transistors NM0, NM1 form a latch and used to store data .NM2, NM3, NM4 are read access transistors. PMOS transistors PM0, PM1 are writing access transistor. An innovative bit line balancing scheme for reading and writing operation of the 7T SRAM cell is also proposed for maximum standby power savings in an SRAM cell [17].our proposed SRAM cell which is introduced in this section is based on 4T SRAM cell, because 4T SRAM cell's power consumption is 29% lower than that of 6T SRAM cell using CMOS technology [18].The schematic 7T SRAM cell is shown in Figure 2. We discuss the write, read and standby cycles for proposed 7T SRAM cell design in more detailed as follows.

Figure 2. Schematic of high read stability 7T SRAM ce

1) Write Cycle

Charging and discharging of BL and BLB for writing '1' and '0' to the storage node. To write '1' to the storage node Q ('0' to QB simultaneously). At first BL and BLB are charge and discharge respectively. Now, WLW is set to low to turn P1 and P2 ON. While, WLR is kept at low voltage to keep N5 OFF. Q is charged up to high level by BL through P1. While, QB is discharged by BLB through P2. When node Q is charged sufficiently, set WLW to high and turn P1 and P2 OFF. For writing '0' to the node 'Q' ('1' to QB simultaneously) BL and BLB are discharged and charged respectively. The wave form of write cycle is shown in Fig3

Figure. 3 Write operation waveform of 7T SRAM cell

2) Read Cycle

In read operation to stores '1' at Q first assert the WLW to high to turn off the P1 and P2 while WLR is maintained at high voltage to keep N5 on whereas BL is discharged through N3 and N5. Whereas BLBAR stays high because N4 insulates BLBAR from the GND. During read operation the storage node Q and QB completely decouple the datum from BL. In contrast, when '0' stores at Q as long as P1 and P2 turning off, and turning N5 on, the BLB is discharged through N4 and N5. We connect a sense amplifier in the schematic of proposed 7T SRAM cell is shown below Figure 3. We get amplified waveform as shown blown in Fig4. Here vout is the output of sense amplifier.

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Fig. 4 Read operation waveform of 7T SRAM cell with sense amplifier

B. 3:8 Adress Decoder

A decoder is a digital logic circuit which takes multiple coded input and converts to coded multiple outputs where the input and output codes are different. The decoding is necessary in applications like data multiplexing, 7 Segment display and memory address decoding. 3X8 decoder is shown in figure3. The simple example of the decoder is an A gate, when all the inputs are high the AND gate output will be high, this output is also known as active high output. A tiny more complex decoder is the 3*8 binary decoders. These decoders convert 3 coded inputs to 8 unique outputs. The figure 3 demonstrates the decoder circuit for 3 coded inputs to 8 coded outputs. It consists of 3 NOT logic gates and 8 AND logic gates. The output of the 3:8 decoders further clarified from its inputs like A, B, C and outputs like D0, D1, D2, D3, D4, D5, D6, D7.

Figure 5. Symbol diagram of 3:8 Decoder

C. 8 Input OR Gate

The OR gate perform logical addition, commonly known as OR function. The OR gate has two or more inputs. The operation of OR gate is such that is high (1) on the output is produced when any of the inputs is high(1). The output is low (0) only when all the inputs are low (0) [20]. In this Array I have used 8 input OR gate which is connected to array's outputs. The output of array acts as the input of the OR gate which perform operation and provides single input.

If A and B are the input variables of an OR gate and Y is its output, then

$$Y=A+B$$

3. Description of Design Parameters In Sram Array

In this segment description of design parameters of SRAM Array like Leakage Current, Leakage Power, Operating Current, Operating Power , Dynamic Current , Dynamic Power , Efficiency.

A. Leakage Current

The subthreshold leakage is the drain-source current of a transistor operating in the weak inversion region. Unlike the strong inversion region in which the drift current dominates, the subthreshold conduction is due to the diffusion current of the minority carriers in the channel for a MOS device. The magnitude of the sub-threshold current is a function of the temperature, supply voltage, device size, and the process parameters out of which the threshold voltage (V_{th}) plays a dominant role.

In current CMOS technologies, the subthreshold leakage current, I_{SUB} , is much larger than the other leakage current components [21]. This is mainly because of the relatively low V_T in modern CMOS devices. I_{SUB} is calculated by using the following formula:

$$I_{DS} = K \left\{ 1 - e^{-\frac{V_{DS}}{V_T}} \right\} e^{\frac{(V_{GS} - V_T + \eta V_{DS})}{nV_T}}$$

Where K and n are functions of the technology, and η is the drain-induced barrier lowering coefficient.

1) Leakage Current at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the leakage current 96.15pA, 225pA and 513.8 pA in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

Figure7. Leakage Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 8. Leakage Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

2) Leakage Current at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the leakage current 91.75pA, 191.1pA and 402.7 pA in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

Figure 9. Leakage Current waveform at supply voltage 0.3v

Figure 10. Leakage Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 11. Leakage Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

B. Leakage Power

Leakage power (P_{leakage} ~ IV), which is the power consumed by unintended leakage that does not contribute to the IC's function. Leakage power is primarily the result of unwanted subthreshold current in the transistor channel when the transistor is turned off. This subthreshold-driven leakage power is strongly influenced by variations in the transistor threshold voltage V_T (the voltage applied to the gate electrode that turns on the transistor).

$$P(V_T) = V_{DD} * I_{OFF}(V_T)$$

Where V_{DD} is the applied voltage and I_{OFF} is the leakage current for a transistor with this value of V_T. The total leakage power dissipated by a group of transistors (such as a product) is therefore the product of the statistical distribution of V_T and the leakage power function P(V_T).

1) Leakage Power at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the leakage power 0.527pW, 1.311pW and 2.684 pW in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

2) Leakage Power at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the leakage power 0.508pW, 0.515pW and 0.518 pW in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

C. Dynamic Current

As the current charges capacitor node voltage start to rise Limiting the current flowing through the transistor until it eventually turns OFF when its voltage becomes zero.

1) Dynamic Current at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the Dynamic Current 104.8nA, 433.3nA and 1.207 μA in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

Figure 12. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.3v

Figure 13. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 14. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

2) Dynamic Current at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the Dynamic Current 53.96nA, 531.8nA and 764.9nA in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

Figure 15. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.3v

Figure 16. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 17. Dynamic Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

D. Dynamic Power

Dynamic power consumption is due to the current that flows only when the transistors of the devices are switching from one logic state to another. This is a result of the current required to charge the internal nodes (switching current) plus the through current (current that flows from VDD to GND when the p-channel transistor and n-channel transistor turn on briefly at the same time during the logic transition). The formula of Dynamic Power shown in below.

$$P_{\text{dyn}} = C_L V_{\text{DD}}^2 f$$

Where VDD is supply voltage, CL (Capacitance) is a Function of fan-out, wire length, transistor sizes and f is Clock frequency.

1) Dynamic Power at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the dynamic power 0.239pW, 17.48pW and 129.7 pW in power supply 0.3V, 0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

2) Dynamic Power at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the dynamic power 0.239pW, 212.9pW and 480 pW in power supply 0.3V, 0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

E. Operating Current

This is the maximum amount of current that SRAM consumes while it is in operation with the V_{dd} at the maximum, the chip select pin active, and output at high impedance. Also known as off-state leakage current and residual current. The amount of current required to keep a sensor active when it is not detecting a target.

1) Operating Current at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the operating current 45.07 μ A, 75.86 μ A and 109.2 μ A in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

Figure 18. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.3v

Figure 19. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 20. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

2) Operating Current at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the operating current $24.63\mu\text{A}$, $39.59\mu\text{A}$ and $43.77\mu\text{A}$ in power supply 0.3V , 0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125GHZ in OR gate structured $8*8$ bit SRAM Array.

Figure 21. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.3v

Figure 22. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.5v

Figure 23. Operating Current waveform at supply voltage 0.7v

F. Operating Power

This is the maximum amount of power that SRAM consumes while it is in operation with the VDD at the maximum, the chip select pin active, and output at high impedance. Also known as off-state leakage power and residual power. The amount of power required to keep a sensor active when it is not detecting a target.

1) Operating Power at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the operating power 27.02nW, 1.55μW and 32.59μW in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

2) Operating Power at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the operating power 224.9pW, 224.9pW and 299pW in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

G. Efficiency

Efficiency in general describes the extent to which time or efforts are well used for the intended task or purpose. Quantitatively determined by the ratio of output to the input.

1) Efficiency at 4ns Access Time

I have estimated the efficiency 61.83%, 95.75% and 98.58% in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 4ns with frequency 0.25 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

2) Efficiency at 8ns Access Time

I have estimated the operating power 71.87%, 86% and 94.69% in power supply 0.3V ,0.5V and 0.7V respectively at 8ns with frequency 0.125 GHZ in OR gate structured 8*8 bit SRAM Array.

4. Impact of Variation in Supply Voltage

Power dissipation is directly proportional to supply voltage. i.e.,

$$P \propto V_{DD}^2$$

Therefore with the decrease in supply voltage, dynamic power, leakage power, operating power will also reduce but in turn increases the delay due to increase in leakage current, operating current and dynamic current flowing through the circuit. If we are reducing the supply voltage as well as efficiency also reduces. At integrated circuit at the prescribed nominal supply voltage is not preferable for reliable circuit operation under access time variation.

5. Simulated Result Summary

Extensive circuit simulations, using CADENCE Virtuoso in 45 nm CMOS process Technology, were performed to confirm the operation of circuit and characterize its performance. We enumerate the 64 bit 7T SRAM Array and estimate the various process parameters. Simulation results are based on 4ns and 8ns Access times with Frequencies 0.25GHZ and 0.125GHz respectively, a

temperature of 27°C and the various supply voltages. The simulated result of 64 bit 7T SRAM Array cell is shown in Table I.

Parameter	OR Gated structured 8 x8 Bit SRAM Array					
	4ns			8ns		
Access Time						
Supply Voltage	0.3V	0.5V	0.7V	0.3V	0.5V	0.7V
Frequency	0.25 GHz	0.25 GHz	0.25 GHz	0.125 GHz	0.125 GHz	0.125 GHz
Leakage Current	96.15 PA	225 PA	513.8 PA	91.75 PA	191.1 PA	402.7 PA
Leakage Power	0.527 PW	1.311 PW	2.684 PW	0.508 PW	0.515 PW	0.518 PW
Dynamic Current	104.8 nA	433.3 nA	1.207 μ A	53.96 nA	531.8 nA	764.9 nA
Dynamic Power	0.239 PW	17.48 PW	129.7 PW	0.239 PW	212.9 PW	480 PW
Operating Current	45.07 μ A	75.86 μ A	109.2 μ A	24.63 μ A	36.59 μ A	43.77 μ A
Operating Power	27.02 nW	1.55 μ W	32.59 μ W	224.9 PW	224.9 PW	299.2 PW
Efficiency %	61.83	95.75	98.58	71.87	86	94.69

6. Conclusion

We have fabricated OR gate structured 8x8 bit 7T SRAM Array using various access time and frequencies with different supply voltages in 45 nm CMOS process technology. We have estimated leakage current, leakage power, Dynamic current, Dynamic power and efficiency of OR gate structured 8x8 bit 7T SRAM Array. We have concluded that, when decrease in supply voltage, dynamic power, leakage power, operating power will also reduce but in turn increases the delay due to increase in leakage current, operating current and dynamic current flowing through the circuit. If we are reducing the supply voltage as well as efficiency also reduces. At integrated circuit at the prescribed nominal supply voltage is not preferable for reliable circuit operation under access time variation. We have concluded that the reduction in power and increase the efficiency of the Static random access memory array.

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